

Global influences and national education policy: perspectives from Croatian pre-service and primary education teachers

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Abstract: *Global processes influence the course of changes in national education policy, and similar reform trends are observed worldwide. Therefore, the first part of the paper provides a brief overview of the main characteristics of global education policy. The aim of this paper is to examine the attitudes of Croatian teacher education students and primary education teachers towards the influence of globalization on national education systems and policies as well as to assess their self-perceived competence to teach global topics. For this purpose, a special questionnaire was created, and a survey was conducted among 113 students and 86 teachers in 2024. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to identify statistically important differences. The results show that the respondents are aware of the influence of globalization and international organizations, especially the European Union, on national education policy. The influence of the European Union on the Croatian education system is mainly perceived as positive. Teaching foreign languages is one of the main characteristics of global education policy, as well as the fact that globalization has created more possibilities for studying abroad and student exchange. The respondents agree that 'brain drain' is the negative consequence of globalization and that education reforms only partially take national values and interests into account. Regarding the self-assessment of competences in teaching global topics, respondents consider themselves most competent to teach about human rights, global inequalities, democracy, and civil society. A lack of competence is noticeable in teaching on modern migrations, and energy to some extent. The results of this research can be used to modernize the programme for teachers' education. The paper contributes to geographical research on the mobility of educational policies between different spatial scales (from global to national).*

Keywords: *global education policy, Europeanization, global competences, pre-service teachers, teachers, geography of education*

Introduction

By changing society, economics, politics, and culture, globalization sets new demands on education, thus influencing the changes in education systems around the world. On the one hand, globalization changes education, but the influences go both ways, which means education is the driving force of global processes. This claim is supported by the famous statement by Nelson Mandela, the first black president of South Africa, which says that 'Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world' (Gebremedhin and Joshi 2016). Education can be the means to minimize negative consequences of globalization by promoting peace and tolerance amongst cultures through educating individuals, helping the fight against climate change, and changing societies towards sustainability (Rocha et al. 2023).

Relations between globalization and education have been the topic of different sciences, from education sciences, sociology of education, and economics to geography. An interest in education exists in different sub-disciplines of human geography, such as economic geography, migration studies, or urban geography (Kučerova, Holloway and Jahnke 2020). Gradually, as a part of human geography, the geography of education has been established as a new discipline in geography, with its research similar to comparative education (Brock 2016), looking into the spatial dimension of education. The geography of education deals with the location of education institutions, educational inequalities in the world, relations between education and development, education and migrations, as well as relations between education and economy (Freitag, Jahnke and Kramer 2015). Almost all research topics of geography of education are related to global processes. For example, global flows of capital, manpower, and ideas create new forms of knowledge concentration in space (e.g., influence the locations of private universities). Globalization can deepen education inequalities in the world since global processes do not affect the space evenly. Local education policy is changed under its influence, which causes national curricula, classes, and evaluation to become standardized (Butt 2011). Globalization encourages student migrations because of education as well as emigrations of experts from less developed countries ('brain drain'). Gulson (2016) and Yoon, Gulson and Lubienski (2018) are among the first to include education policy research into geographic analysis, researching how global trends in education 'descend' from the global to national and local levels. Furthermore, the authors emphasize the role of GIS in spatial education analysis. Geographer Brock (2016) and later McKenzie and Aikens (2021) started thinking about the vertical mobility of education policies among different spatial scales (global, national, regional, local). Therefore, there is some interest in geography for considering the process and influence of globalization on education from different perspectives (Taylor 2009).

Globalization and Europeanization of education policy: processes, actors and implications

Values which promote national education systems are no longer defined only by political actors within the national state. Although education policy was exclusively a national matter until recently, nowadays it is shaped in a global context. The matter of fact is that national governments still create education policies, but in ways that acknowledge global trends (Rizvi and Lingard 2009).

In the last three decades, there have been changes in the ways of development, implementation and evaluation of education policies (Rizvi and Lingard 2009). National education policies and systems are under the influence of global factors such as human capital, multiculturalism, inter-governmental organizations, media, information and communication technology, non-government organizations, and trans-national companies (Spring 2009, according to Kaymakci 2012). Furthermore, global expansion of the free market is omnipresent, resulting in economic and financial integration, which leads to the strengthening of supranational grouping, while at the same time, common agendas are used increasingly as means of solving crucial problems in the world (Spajić-Vrkaš 1999).

The listed factors have caused the implementation of similar education reforms around the world. The set of common education reforms implemented in distant and culturally and economically very different countries is known as the Global Education Policy (GEP). This term was created at the turn of the 21st century, and it can be considered as a group of 'global education agendas' (Kanić and Kovač 2017, Verger, Novelli and Altinyelken 2018, Tromp and Datzberger 2021). Education policy and reform processes have the goal to strengthen the global competitiveness of a national state (Al'Abri 2011, Pang 2013).

Various international organizations (e.g., UN, OECD, EU) are becoming leading political actors that act as mediators to global education agendas, providing guidelines for shaping

education policy (Rizvi and Lingard 2009, Kovač et al. 2014, Kanić and Kovač 2017). International organizations have an extensive role by offering education programmes as well as by being the biggest providers of assistance for education reforms. For countries to get the financial aid from certain organizations, it is necessary to implement their policies and programmes (Al'Abri 2011). For instance, since 2023, an Experimental programme 'Primary school as all-day school' has been implemented in Croatia involving about 60 primary schools, and the aim is to improve the quality of the education system according to challenges of the 21st century. The implementation of the all-day school model is financially and from the organizational point of view supported by the finances provided by the European Social Fund and a loan from the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (MZO 2023).

Changes in education, directly or indirectly caused by globalization, are numerous. There are tendencies towards privatization and marketing of education, growth of management in schools and universities, or, in other words, the implementation of business models in education services (Smith 2002). Carnoy (1999) states that globalization changes the organization of work, which demands a higher level of education of the workforce and constant acquisition of new skills. To be globally competitive, companies and workers have to change, and a changeable workplace demands education and training of 'knowledge workers' (Wilson 2005). Briefly put, in an economy based on knowledge, lifelong education plays an important role. Furthermore, globalization encourages the increase in the number of university students, more investments in education, comparison of the quality of education systems on an international level, implementation of information and communication technologies, etc. (Carnoy 1999). English is promoted as a global language and primary communication medium in science and stronger internationalization of education as well, for example, through the rise of international mobility of students (Rizvi and Lingard 2009). The internationalization of curriculum is happening, meaning that there is the implementation of intercultural and global dimensions in the curriculum, along with the learning outcomes, task assessments, and teaching methods (Leask 2015). It can be claimed that multiculturalism is penetrating education, programmes for civic studies and sustainable development are being developed, etc. In a word, in the last thirty years or so, demands for global education and global learning have been appearing.

Education has a crucial role in the preparation of children and youth for life in the globalized world of the future (Gu 2021), which causes the development of different concepts of global education. For instance, the North-South Centre of the Council of Europe introduces the Global Education Charter (1997) and the Maastricht Global Education Declaration (2002), thus developing its concept of global education (Cabezudo et al. 2019). Furthermore, in Europe, since 2001, there has been a network of European ministries and agencies, Global Education Network Europe (GENE), which gathers the creators of national policies to improve global education (Scheunpflug and Wegimont 2024). On the other hand, UNESCO has been promoting a programme entitled Global Citizenship Education (GCED) since 2011 (UNESCO 2015).

Although there are different concepts of global education, they have a common aim to create a global citizen, which means that pupils need to acquire a set of global competences. According to a frequently quoted Oxfam's 'Curriculum for Global Citizenship', first published in the United Kingdom in 1997, a global citizen is aware of the wider world and his role as the citizen of the world; respects and honours diversity; understands how the world functions - economically, politically, socially, culturally, technologically and ecologically; is indignant due to social injustice; participates and contributes in the community on different levels, from local to global; is willing to act to make the world a more just and sustainable place; takes the responsibility for his actions (Oxfam 1997 according Oxfam 2015). In 2018, the most famous international research on education, PISA, included the examination of global competences of pupils for the first time (OECD 2020).

Alongside the globalization processes on the European continent, there is the process of Europeanization caused by the creation of the European Union. Since the last decade of the 20th century, when the European Union in today's sense was formed by the Maastricht Declaration (1992), the processes of creation of the common European space in different social areas have been strengthened. Even though the European Union does not have a common education policy, which means that state members are still responsible for the teaching content and the formation of education systems, the Maastricht Declaration established the aims of the European Union in the field of education (EU 1992). The Lisbon Strategy from 2000 established several tasks of European education policy: promotion of lifelong learning, larger investments in education, development of local centres for learning, development of new basic skills, and an increase in qualification transparency (Žiljak 2006).

Probably the best example of Europeanization in the field of education is the Bologna process started in 1999 whose aim is to bring national systems of higher education into harmony, the creation of common European higher education area (EHEA) and European research area (ERA) as well as the implementation of mobility programmes (e.g. Erasmus for students) (Carlson, Eigmüller and Lueg 2018). Whilst the Bologna process is focused on higher education, the Copenhagen process was started in 2002 to improve the European cooperation in vocational education and training and better its quality and attractiveness (Bainbridge 2024). As far as the Europeanization of education policies is concerned, the listed processes are connected to the European Qualifications Framework implemented in 2008. In 2013, when Croatia became a member of the European Union, a Croatian qualification frame was implemented based on the guidelines of the European qualification frame, as well as the Croatian educational tradition and needs of its economy and society.

Methodology

Research framework and aim

Education geography research can include different participants of the education system and all levels of education, from preschool to primary and secondary, all the way to university and lifelong education (Holloway and Jöns 2012). Primary education in the Croatian education system includes the period from the first to fourth grade of elementary school. Even though it is traditionally focused on the local content, it is influenced by globalization on many levels. Global education trends and digital technologies, accompanied by the eradication of national identity, increasingly shape the curriculum and teaching methods (Matas 2006). Changes in the local communities, like migrations, effects of climate change, cultural diversities, and digital connections, bring global challenges into elementary school classrooms.

Ideas promoted by global education are taught in the Croatian education system through different teaching subjects in cross-curricular topics like Personal and Social Development, Civic Education, and Sustainable Development (MZO 2019). As far as geographic education in Croatia is concerned, it is implemented in Science and Social Studies at the beginning of the education process. Even though this subject puts emphasis on local and national geography, its cross-curricular approach realizes some of the ideas of global education.

Teacher education programmes need to be coordinated with the principles of global education to prepare them for teaching on global problems, thus contributing to the creation of 'global citizens'. Teachers need knowledge and skills in the field of geography, history, foreign languages, up-to-date global issues, and pedagogy to get to know the ways of teaching on global problems (Kaymakci 2012).

The aim of this paper is to research the attitudes of students of teacher studies and primary education teachers towards the influence of globalization on national education systems and policies as well as to establish how the respondents estimate their competence to teach on global topics.

Participants

A total of 199 respondents participated in the research conducted in 2024. The research sample is a convenience sample, consisting of 113 students of the final year of teacher studies (5th year), which means future teachers of primary education from two Croatian universities (University of Zagreb, University of Slavonski Brod) and 86 primary education teachers from various primary schools in continental Croatia. As far as the sex of the respondents is concerned, there were 96% female and 3% male students. Females prevail amongst teachers as well, with 94.2%, while there were 3.5% of males. According to work experience in education, 17.4% of teachers have been employed for 10 years or less, 27.9% between 11 and 20 years, 18.6% between 21 and 30 years, and 33.7% have been working in education for more than 30 years (the balance to total refers to the unknown).

Instrument and the statistics analysis

For this research, a special questionnaire was constructed. Items in the questionnaire are shaped by studying relevant literature on the relations between globalization and education, as well as by the author's previous research in that scientific area (e.g., Braičić 2012, Cvitanović, Lončar and Braičić 2022). In this way, the research contains the key dimensions of the relations between globalization and education in the context of national states, which strived to ensure the content validity of the questionnaire.

The questionnaire consisted of four parts. The first part collected general data on the sex of the respondents and the years of experience of the teachers. The next part of the questionnaire contained a multiple-choice task. The respondents were supposed to choose the most important symbols of globalization in their opinion, out of several offers. The third part contained 17 items, or claims, arranged in three groups (the attitude of respondents to the influence of globalization on the changes in education systems; respondents' attitude to globalization influence on Croatia and its education system; respondents' attitude to global education policy). The respondents expressed their attitude to each claim on Likert's scale of 5 degrees (from 1 – do not agree to 5 – completely agree, and for the estimate on globalization influence on Croatia from 1 – strongly negative to 5 – strongly positive). The fourth part contained 8 items referring to self-evaluation of the competence to teach on global topics. The respondents estimated their competence on Likert's scale of 4 degrees (from 1 – completely incompetent to 4 – extremely competent). In the end, the respondents were asked to list the classes that provided knowledge and skills on globalization and global problems during their studies (open question only for the students).

The data collected through the questionnaire was processed through the programme for statistical analysis of sampled data, GNU PSPP 1.4.1-g79ad47. The normality of the distribution of the data frequency was tested by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Since it was established that the results are not normally distributed, non-parametric statistics (Mann-Whitney U test for independent samples) were used to establish statistically important differences. The level of statistical importance was set to $p < 0.05$.

Results

In order to gain a general insight into the perception of globalization, the respondents were offered a choice of about twenty potential symbols of globalization. They referred to the economy, modern technologies and global media, regional integration, global culture and sports, etc. Some symbols of globalization used in the questionnaire were taken from the Fülöp paper (2011). The task was to mark which ones, in respondents' opinion, are the main symbols of globalization.

As presented in fig. 1, today the main symbols of globalization are social networks and the Internet, followed by two economic symbols of globalization – the Euro and multinational

companies. The next on the list of symbols is the European Union, considered a symbol of globalization by twice as many respondents as the United Nations, as an old international organization. No wonder that the Euro currency and the European Union are highly perceived as symbols of globalization since the processes of Europeanization in Croatia have been in full swing for the last twenty years. In 2013, Croatia became a member of the European Union, and it is its newest member, while the Euro, as a new official currency, was not introduced until 2023. Erasmus, the programme for student and teacher exchange, was recognized as a symbol of globalization in a mediocre manner. As far as modern technologies and media are concerned, streaming service Netflix, one of the leading contemporary world media, is relatively highly ranked, while previously globally popular media company MTV television is not recognized as an important symbol of globalization. This media company was globally and culturally important in the 1980s and partially in the 1990s.

Fig. 1. What do you consider the main symbols of globalization out of the listed? (N=199);
Note: multiple answer possibility; %for each answer separately in relation to total number of respondents

The continuation shows the results of research on the respondents' attitudes towards the influence of globalization on education and changes in education systems (tab. 1). The results of the descriptive parameters shows that the respondents are aware of the influence of globalization on education (M=3.87, SD=.79) and that national education policy is significantly under the influence of international organizations (M=3.67, SD=.90). However, according to the height of arithmetic means the respondents even more distinctly emphasize the influences of the European Union (M=3.97, SD=.83) believing that European Union institutions have more influence on national education policy than other international organizations and globalization in general. Even though the European Union does not have its own education policy, the fact is that there are certain influences on education policies. Such respondents' beliefs can partially be assigned to the fact that Croatia is the newest member of the European Union,

which causes a high evaluation of the processes of Europeanization. Furthermore, most respondents agree with the claim that globalization contributes to 'brain drain' as one of the frequently emphasized negative consequences of globalization. The claim that the least respondents agreed with is that education reforms acknowledge national interests and values ($M=3.17$, $SD=1.00$). It should be added that the respondents' beliefs on this question are rather divided; on the one hand, 38.7% of respondents agreed with this claim, while at the same time, 28.1% do not agree with it, and 31.2% are undecided.

Tab. 1. Attitudes of students of teacher studies and primary education teachers on the influence of globalization on the changes in education systems – descriptive statistics ($N=199$)

Items	Min.	Max.	M	SD	Me	Mo
Education systems of national countries change under the influence of globalization	1	5	3.87	0.79	4.00	4
National education policy is under the influence of international organizations (e.g., UN, OECD)	1	5	3.67	0.90	4.00	4
European Union institutions influence the education policies of member countries	1	5	3.97	0.83	4.00	4
Education reforms take into consideration national values and interests	1	5	3.17	1.00	4.00	3
The aim of education reforms is to improve the global competitiveness of the national state	1	5	3.42	0.87	4.00	4
Globalization contributes to 'brain drain'	1	5	3.95	0.90	4.00	4

The Mann-Whitney U test was used to establish whether there are statistically important differences between the attitudes of students of teacher studies and primary education teachers. Attitudes of students and teachers on the influence of globalization on education and education systems are statistically significantly different for the last three claims (tab. 2): education reforms take into consideration national values and interests ($U=3799.00$; $Z=-2.34$; $p=.019$), the aim of education reforms is to improve global competitiveness of the national state ($U=3933.50$; $Z=-2.46$; $p=.014$) and globalization contributes to 'brain drain' ($U=3917.50$; $Z=-2.35$; $p=.019$). Statistically significant difference occurs due to more negative teachers' attitudes towards the influence of globalization on education in comparison to students' attitudes. For example, based on the answer frequency, it was established that 18.6% of students and even 40.7% teachers do not agree with the claim that education reforms take into consideration national values and interests. Even though only 7.1% of students do not agree with the claim that the aim of education reforms is to improve the competitiveness of the national state, 25.6% of teachers do not agree with the same claim. Finally, a larger number of teachers emphasize that globalization contributes to 'brain drain' (82.6%) than students, future teachers (61%). The young take into consideration the globalization phenomenon comprehending its multiple possibilities for their personal and professional development, while the older are more constrained about that question (Schubarth et al. 2011, Breaz 2019, Uphues 2020).

The results show that the respondents are not synchronized on the question of whether the influences of globalization are more positive or negative (tab. 3). There is almost an equal number of those who consider the influence of globalization on Croatia in general (1), its national economy (2), and education (3) as mainly positive or negative. Most items are of average value according to the arithmetic mean, which means that there are no major differences in respondents' attitudes between some claims. According to their opinion, globalization influences Croatia in general, its national economy, and education policy equally in both positive and negative ways. However, it has to be noticed that the EU influences on Croatian education policy (4) are perceived more positively.

Tab. 2. Differences in perception of the influence of globalization on education systems between students of teacher studies and primary education teachers (Mann-Whitney U test)

Items		Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	MWU	Z	p
Education systems of national states change under the influence of globalization.	Students	94.21	10645.50	4204.50	-1.69	0.091
	Teachers	106.54	9055.50			
National education policy is under the influence of international organizations (e.g., UN, OECD).	Students	96.86	10945.50	4504.50	-0.95	0.341
	Teachers	104.12	8954.50			
European Union organizations influence the education policies of the member states.	Students	101.75	11497.50	4661.50	-0.54	0.590
	Teachers	97.70	8402.50			
Education reforms take into consideration national values and interests.	Students	105.96	11656.00	3799.00	-2.34	0.019
	Teachers	87.69	7454.00			
The aim of the education reforms is to improve global competitiveness of the national state.	Students	108.19	12225.50	3933.50	-2.46	0.014
	Teachers	89.24	7674.50			
Globalization contributes to 'brain drain'.	Students	91.67	10358.50	3917.50	-2.35	0.019
	Teachers	109.91	9342.50			

Tab. 3. Attitudes of future teachers and primary education teachers on the influence of globalization on the Republic of Croatia – descriptive statistics (N=199)

Items	Min.	Max.	M	SD	Me	Mo
The influence of globalization on Croatia in general	2	5	2.99	.71	3.00	3
The influence of globalization on the Croatian economy	1	4	2.88	.84	3.00	3
The influence of globalization on the changes in the Croatian education system	1	5	3.02	.74	3.00	3
EU influence on education policy in Croatia	1	5	3.20	.74	3.00	3

The Mann-Whitney test did not confirm the existence of statistically important differences between students' and teachers' attitudes. Although the differences are not statistically important, based on the answer frequencies, it is obvious that students experience the influences of globalization on Croatian education policy more positively than teachers with practice (fig. 2). 31% of students and only 20.9% of teachers think that globalization has a positive influence on education. Along with that, a larger number of students (38.9%) as opposed to teachers (29.1%) believe that globalization has a negative influence on the Croatian economy. Opposed to students' opinion, teachers believe that globalization has a more positive influence on the economy than on education in Croatia. However, both groups of respondents experience the influence of the EU on education policy as positive (only 16% of students and 14% of teachers believe that the influence is negative).

The main characteristics of global education policy are identified for the needs of this research through examining the professional and scientific literature. The respondents' task was to estimate to what extent they agree with the listed items (tab. 4). The results of the descriptive parameters showed that the respondents mainly agree with all the listed trends of global education policy. Over 80% of the respondents believe that learning foreign languages is a part of global education policy (M=4.32, SD=.75), that globalization encourages international student exchange (M=4.21, SD=.73) and that globalization means more possibilities for studying abroad (M=4.11, SD=.77). More than 70% of the respondents believe that globalization encourages intercultural education (M=3.83, SD=.80). Somewhat lower arithmetic means are

recorded on the claims that global education policy is targeted at civic studies, sustainable development and lifelong studies. Despite that, most respondents agree with those claims as well.

Fig. 2. Parallel presentation of students' and teachers' attitudes on the influence of globalization on the Republic of Croatia - frequencies in % (N=199)

Tab. 4. Attitudes of students of teacher studies and primary education teachers on the characteristics of global education policy – descriptive statistics (N=199)

Items	Min.	Max.	M	SD	Me	Mo
Global education policy is aimed at lifelong learning	1	5	3.59	0.95	4.00	4
Global education policy is aimed at sustainable development	1	5	3.64	0.84	4.00	4
Learning foreign languages is a part of global education policy	2	5	4.32	0.75	4.00	5
Global education policy is aimed at civic studies	1	5	3.65	0.80	4.00	4
Globalization encourages multicultural/intercultural education	2	5	3.83	0.80	4.00	4
Globalization means more possibilities for studying abroad	2	5	4.11	0.77	4.00	4
Globalization encourages international student exchange	2	5	4.21	0.73	4.00	4

The results have shown that there is no statistically significant difference between student and teacher candidates' opinions on most claims about the characteristics of global education policy. Their attitudes on global education policy are statistically significantly different on the following two claims (tab. 5): learning foreign languages is a part of global education policy ($U=3989.50$; $Z=-2.14$; $p=.032$) and globalization encourages international student exchange ($U=3928.50$; $Z=-2.25$; $p=.024$). A statistically significant difference was established even though both groups of respondents agreed with both claims in a high percentage. Through the insight into average ranks and frequencies of answers, it becomes clear that students agree with these claims on a slightly larger scale. 92% of students and 78.4% of teachers believe that learning foreign languages is a part of global education policy, and 85.8% of students and

81.4% teachers believe that globalization encourages international student exchange. The English language has become a part of everyday communication among youth, which means students as well. Therefore, the difference in the attitude toward learning foreign languages can be explained by the age difference between the two groups of respondents (e.g., the teacher specimen included over 30% of those with 30 or more years of work experience). Furthermore, it is not difficult to presume that the student population is more familiar with the possibilities of international student exchange, so it is not surprising that there is a statistically significant difference in this item as well.

Tab. 5. Differences in the perception of global education policy between students of teacher studies and primary education teachers (Mann-Whitney U test)

Items		Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	MWU	Z	p
Global education policy is aimed at life-long learning.	Students	101.15	11430.00	4616.00	-0.50	0.619
	Teachers	97.31	8271.00			
Global education policy is aimed at sustainable development.	Students	99.23	11213.00	4772.00	-0.08	0.933
	Teachers	99.86	8488.00			
Learning foreign languages is a part of global education policy.	Students	105.88	11858.50	3989.50	-2.14	0.032
	Teachers	89.94	7644.50			
Global education policy is aimed at civic studies.	Students	97.02	10963.50	4522.50	-0.77	0.441
	Teachers	102.79	8737.50			
Globalization encourages multicultural/intercultural education.	Students	101.78	11501.00	4432.00	-0.88	0.381
	Teachers	95.26	8002.00			
Globalization means more possibilities for studying abroad.	Students	102.30	11560.00	4486.00	-0.88	0.380
	Teachers	95.78	8141.00			
Globalization encourages the international students exchange.	Students	106.23	12004.50	3928.50	-2.25	0.024
	Teachers	89.27	7498.50			

The last part of the questionnaire requested the respondents to assess their competence to teach on certain global topics. The results show that respondents are prone to lean towards the claim which considers them partially competent to teach on most global topics (tab. 6). According to arithmetic mean the respondents perceive themselves the most competent to teach on human rights ($M=3.30$, $SD=.59$), inequalities round the world ($M=3.12$, $SD=.77$), then on democracy and civic society ($M=3.07$, $SD=.69$), etc. It became known from the answer frequency that over 90% of the respondents consider themselves partially or extremely competent to teach on human rights, and around 80% of them to teach on inequalities around the world, democracy, and world peace. A slightly smaller number consider themselves competent on the problems of sustainable development and climate change. The respondents consider themselves the least competent to teach on modern migrations (only 54.3%) and energy problems (64.3%).

Statistically important difference between the competences of students and teachers was established by Mann-Whitney test in only one case – on the question of teaching on modern migrations (tab. 7). Even though both groups stated the lack of competences to teach on modern migrations, it can be noticed from the average ranks that students (Mean Rank = 105.86) consider themselves more competent to teach on this topic than teachers (Mean Rank = 88.69). The results also showed that there are no statistically significant differences between the competencies of teachers with less work experience (20 years or less) and those with more work experience (21 years or more).

Tab. 6. *Self-assessment of the competence of future teachers and primary education teachers to teach on global topics – descriptive statistics*

Items	Min.	Max.	M	SD	Me	Mo
World peace	2	4	3.05	0.73	3.00	3
Human rights	2	4	3.30	0.59	3.00	3
Democracy and civic society	1	4	3.07	0.69	3.00	3
Sustainable development	1	4	2.97	0.70	3.00	3
Climate changes	1	4	2.91	0.77	3.00	3
Modern migrations	1	4	2.68	0.77	3.00	2
World inequalities	1	4	3.12	0.69	3.00	3
Energy	1	4	2.79	0.77	3.00	3

Tab. 7. *Differences in the self-assessment of competences to teach on global topics between future teachers and primary education teachers (Mann-Whitney U test)*

Items		Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	MWU	Z	p
World peace	Students	99.77	11274.00	4659.00	-0.24	0.807
	Teachers	97.96	8229.00			
Human rights	Students	100.70	11379.00	4554.00	-0.55	0.580
	Teachers	96.71	8124.00			
Democracy and civic society	Students	96.99	10863.00	4535.00	-0.47	0.636
	Teachers	100.51	8443.00			
Sustainable development	Students	97.32	10997.00	4556.00	-0.68	0.498
	Teachers	102.40	8704.00			
Climate changes	Students	105.12	11879.00	4054.00	-1.88	0.060
	Teachers	90.76	7624.00			
Modern migrations	Students	105.86	11856.00	3880.00	-2.26	0.024
	Teachers	88.69	7450.00			
World inequalities	Students	105.50	11921.00	4125.00	-1.87	0.061
	Teachers	91.53	7780.00			
Energy	Students	98.33	11013.00	4685.00	-0.20	0.838
	Teachers	99.88	8490.00			

In order to make teacher candidates competent to teach on global problems, programmes on teacher studies are synchronized with the principles of global education. New topics and approaches like civic studies, upbringing for differences, class and school management, teachers' leadership, etc., are introduced (Vizek Vidović and Domović 2013). Teacher education programmes contain courses directly or indirectly dealing with the topics of global education. Final year students in teacher studies in Croatia have singled out the courses that provided knowledge and skills referring to global topics and problems. Some of them are: Geography, Science, Methodology of Science and Social Studies, Introduction to Culture and Civilization, Education Sociology, Multiculturalism and European Identities, General Pedagogy, Philosophy of Upbringing, and Basics of Intercultural Communication. Students also listed some elective courses like World Religions and Education for Democratic Citizens.

Discussion

The aim of this research was to question the attitudes of Croatian pre-service and primary education teachers to the influences of globalization on national education systems as well as to establish how the respondents estimate their competence to teach on global topics. Although the papers theoretically dealing with the questions of the relations between globalization and education are well represented, studies researching attitudes of students, teachers or educators on the influences of globalization on education are relatively rare. Therefore, the results of this research contribute to a better understanding of the relations between globalization processes and education from the perspective of teachers and students as participants in the education process.

Research results have pointed out that the respondents are aware of the existing influences of globalization on education, even though in some instances they expressed their attitudes through medium grades, or in other words, they neither agreed nor disagreed with some statements. This can indicate a lack of knowledge and experience on some aspects of globalization and its influence on education policy. By researching the perception of teachers in Turkey, Öztürk and Günel (2016) came to a similar conclusion, whose results pointed out the lack of knowledge on global systems and global education. However, neutral answers can indicate ambivalence of the respondents who notice both positive and negative effects at the same time, and do not want to commit themselves to either side. Since the used methodology does not enable insight into reasons for expressing attitudes through neutral answers, their explanation remains open to further, especially qualitative research.

The results of research presented in this paper enable the conclusion that the influences of globalization on education are perceived as equally positive and negative. Such a pattern indicates a polarization of attitudes resulting from different value frameworks. There will always be those who will perceive globalization as an opportunity for development and modernization (pro-globalists), while others will emphasize risks to national values and educational autonomy (anti-globalists). Even though the influences of globalization on education are mainly considered equally positive and negative, the results have indicated that future teachers perceive them slightly more positively than teachers. Different research studies have also established that the younger generation has a more positive attitude toward the effects of globalization (e.g., Breaz, 2019; Uphues, 2020; Schubarth et al., 2011).

The affirmation of foreign language learning, contribution to international student exchange and larger possibilities of studying abroad are listed as positive effects of globalization. As far as the negative effects are concerned, the respondents mainly agree that globalization contributes to brain drain and that global reforms insufficiently acknowledge national values. Numerous studies around the world have established that teachers in general positively perceive the influence of globalization on education and the teaching profession, but at the same time indicated the concern about the domination of Western values, that the imposed policies do not respect local and national context enough, and that globalization alienates teachers from their values and culture (e.g., Matsopoulos et al. 2018, Gürdoğan-Bayır, Göz and Bozkurt 2014, Roth and Rönnström 2015, Canli and Demirtaş 2018).

Numerous authors focus on the influences of globalization on changes in educating future teachers (McGaha and Linder 2014, Öztürk and Günel 2016, Canli and Demirtaş 2018, Douglas-Gardner and Callender 2023). At the same time, they emphasize the need to improve their global competencies and implement global education in teacher training programs (e.g., Parmigiani et al. 2022, Kerkhoff and Cloud 2020, O'Connor and Zeichner 2011). Future teachers need the knowledge, skills and values in order to help pupils to peacefully resolve conflicts, respect mutual dignity and cultural diversity, and to become socially responsible citizens (Kumar and Parveen 2013). Curriculum for teacher training should include the use of technology in teaching, foreign languages, comparative education, international exchange programme, etc. (Pant and Gusain 2014). The results of our research indicate that the teachers mostly consider themselves partially competent to teach on most global topics. By researching the importance of competences of teachers in Croatia, Kovač, Rafajac and Buchberger (2014) con-

clude that global competences represent an important part of their competence profile. Teachers believe that recognizing global trends in education and understanding their effects on teaching activities and school practice are extremely important. Through researching the perception of Greek teachers concerning global and intercultural competences, Karanikola, Katsioli and Palaiologou (2022) also state that teachers are aware of their enormous importance in the growth of society, but at the same time consider themselves insufficiently prepared to teach global and intercultural content.

The Bologna process influenced the changes in teacher training in numerous European countries, including Croatia. With that process, teacher training programmes were synchronized with European standards, which were mainly the result of global trends (Domović, Knežević and Cvikić 2024). Although the contents of global education are represented in several courses in the teacher education curriculum in Croatia, it should be noted that those new teacher training programmes were introduced twenty years ago (academic year 2005/2006). During that period, there were several smaller and larger reforms in primary schools in Croatia, including the introduction of a cross-curricular topics curriculum with the elements of global education. Teacher education curricula are adjusting to those changes at a much slower pace.

The research on global competences in this paper had an exploratory character. Therefore, the results of this research can serve as a guideline for further improvements of the teacher education curriculum, but also open up space for deeper research into global competencies.

Conclusion

In the world that changes rapidly and is more connected than ever before, global processes influence the changes in all areas of life and significantly influence the direction of changes in national education policy. Similar changes in education can be noticed around the world, and among other things, the curriculum is changing due to the implementation of global dimensions. Students need to gain a set of competences to be not only aware of the world's problems but also be able to critically think about global happenings and act for social benefit. School has an important role in the creation of a global citizen, consequently causing the synchronization of the programmes of teacher studies with the principles of global education.

The results of this research show that the teacher candidates and primary education teachers are aware of the influence of globalization on education and the shaping of national education policy. Even though the influences of globalization on education policy in Croatia are basically perceived as neither extremely positive nor negative, it can be noticed that teacher candidates see them as slightly more positive than the teachers. This result can partially be explained by the fact that the older people (teachers) are usually more sceptical towards globalization than the young (students). Furthermore, teacher candidates are not an active part of the education system, so it is possible that they have not had the opportunity to gain a quality insight into the unwanted repercussions of globalization on education. Teacher candidates also evaluate the influence of globalization on the Croatian education system as more positive than its influence on the Croatian economy. Opposite to students' opinion, teachers believe that globalization brings slightly more benefits for the national economy than for education. When the influences of the European Union on Croatian education policy are concerned, both groups of respondents judge them as more positive than the influences of globalization in general. Such a result is partially attributed to focusing the attention of Croatian citizens on the European Union since Croatia is its newest member.

To a large extent, the respondents consider themselves competent to teach on most global topics, especially on human rights, world inequalities, democracy and civic society. They consider themselves slightly less competent to teach on modern migrations and energy problems in the world. Teacher candidates pointed out that they gained the most knowledge on global problems during the Geography course in teacher studies. Providing an insight into the level of competences, the research results can be used to modernize the teacher education programme and the creation of a lifelong learning programme.

This research has its limitations. It is based on the method of self-assessment of the competences and at the same time limited to the population of students of teacher studies and primary education teachers. Future research on teaching competences on global topics should include other methods of measurement, such as knowledge tests, real-life situation simulation, etc. (Ricijaš et al. 2006). Besides the teacher population, the research could be extended to the examination of attitudes of teachers of different subjects on globalization and education (e.g., students and teachers of Geography, History), as well as the self-assessment of their competences.

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